

LINGUISTIC POLITICAL PROGNOSTICS: MODELS AND SCENARIOS OF FUTURE

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Abstract.

The present paper briefly recalls theoretical preconditions for forming a new approach – linguistic political prognostics. The authors review theories and methods used for strengthening a future focus in political discourses and work out two main tools – a model of future and a scenario of future

Keywords.

linguistic political prognostics; cognitive linguistics; future research; political discourse

The future is obviously a feature of our understanding time. Time is inseparable from the person, it models the person as a social being, and the person in his turn models time and consequently there is always a temptation to sense and predict future. Nowadays the problem of future has emerged with the utmost urgency. Faced with the complexities and challenges of the times, much effort has gone into the development of models and scenarios through which to comprehend the future of a country and to guide the navigation of policy-makers. Core analytical concepts include visions, projections, forecasts and plans, and continuities of past, present and future. In the world of forecasts, the object of our analysis is political projections, with Russia's political system and political processes being their main targets. Essential distinctions among the notions "vision, projection, and forecast" are proposed by A. Isserman. A projection is not a prediction but merely the result of entering hypothetical assumptions into a mechanistic quantitative procedure. Projections are not predictions of the way the future must or will unfold. They are only mechanical exercises that spell out the future implications of current trends or past ratios without assessing the validity of assumptions used to make this or that projection. A string of recent articles and books has stressed prospective functions of political discourse. That's due to the fact that politicians and journalists often reckon the experience of their

predecessors, try to evaluate the present situation and either promise «extrinsic benefits that are contingent on a candidate's victory in the election» or threaten the public with coming catastrophes. E. Lassan points out that the triple opposition "past-present-future" is one of the most important valuable oppositions contemporary political discourse based upon. Insights into prospective function of political discourse can be drawn from D. Graber who holds that any political discourse includes prediction of the future and reflection on the past. G. Lakoff places the future among five implicit categories that define both a progressive culture and a progressive form of government, and encompass all progressive policies. That is the moral perspective. A. Chudinov stresses a structuring function of the metaphor.

He has come to an understanding that metaphors play a crucial role in framing world models and comprehending interrelation between their elements. T. Shmeleva thinks "communicative future" to be an integral part of any speech genre. E. Sheygal considers proclamation of political policy for the future among the dominant characteristics of inaugural speech. V. Dauletova exploring the genre of political autobiography also pays special attention to "communicative future". The advantage of the cognitive approach is the ability to determine mental schemas or cognitive models underlying any political text. The structure and content of these cognitive models are important to effectively study the mode of thinking of those who represent political and non-political institutions in a particular historical period. They also help to build "predictive models in political science". A growing number of recent linguists have been trying to establish metaphor at a cognitive level. One of the fundamental findings of cognitive science is that people think in terms of frames and metaphors.

G. Lakoff places the human act of cognition in the center of attention; his brilliantly presented result is that cognition is vitally dependent on metaphor, which he defines as a mapping of conceptual structures from one domain onto another. He says that framing is about getting language that fits your worldview. The ideas are primary – the language carries and evokes those ideas. Scholars stress the crucial importance of metaphor in discourse interaction: many accounts of figurative schemas and language are concerned with: (a) what is conceptualized in terms of something else and how this process takes place; (b) exploring metaphors in various genres of political discourse; (c) cognitive rhetoric, etc. Metaphorical thinking is to some extent necessary and unavoidable; it advocates a critical stance with respect to the utilization and circulation of metaphor, shaping the future at the same time. Linguistic political future research is concerned with elaborating models

and scenarios of future in political discourse of different chronological periods. A model is used as a tool to get an idea of possible options for future development of society, helps to better understand the driving forces shaping it. In other words such a model is a kind of identification of drivers and trends. The metamodel used in the approach is a matrix –“methodology of forecasting and historical models” covering the evolution of various parameters of Russian socio-political system.

Many different trends occupy the same historical time line. Examples include population, housing, changing technology, financial markets, and the rise and fall of political regimes. These parallel trends are not independent and are clearly linked. Forecasts often address only a limited set of possible trends, focusing on one part of the future to the exclusion of other factors. As the authors' interest is political discourse, the process of constructing the metamodel includes creating a conceptual model of political future. Its basic components are domestic and foreign policies. Basic parameters in their turn can be divided into subsets – factors most frequently addressed in mass media when referring to the image of Russia's future as the main force at home and abroad that form the image of Russia and its possible political future is Russian-sensitive mass media. These subsets are quite numerous. In order to reduce the level of complexity they therefore have to be grouped into some generic categories. So the basic parameter “foreign policy” is divided into the following subsets: relations with the USA, relations with Europe, relations with CIS (“near abroad”), relations with Asian countries. The basic parameter “domestic policy”, in its turn, can be divided into the subsets: political and economic situation, population, natural resources, and armed forces.

Models are constructed for each historical period analyzed. They are based on the data obtained from a particular discourse– Russian, American or British – of a certain chronological period. These are static matrices used to compare differences and similarities of models in political discourses of Russia, the US and Britain. They represent a system of conceptual assumptions concerning a hypothetic situation in Russia's future from the standpoint of the present or the past. To interpret this or that political discourse is to know its background, to understand expectations of the author and the audience, their hidden motives, plot schemes and favorite logic transitions typical of a particular historicera. A cognitive scenario, as it has been stated above, is a sort of linguistic representation and verbalization of each conceptual model. Scenario-writing is especially useful to politicians as a way of sensitizing themselves to various possibilities of the future, which can then be planned for (or against). Scenarios can be either state or process driven. State scenarios are those that offer a vision of what the world will be like at a specified

point in the future without describing the process by which this end state is achieved (in the present research these are scenarios constructed for a static model). By contrast, process scenarios describe the circumstances and sequence of events through which a particular vision or end state is realized.

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